

Teachers' Perception of Guidance Services offered by Counsellors in Secondary Schools in Ahoada-East and Ahoada-West Local Government Areas of Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined teachers' perception of guidance services offered by counsellors in secondary schools in Ahoada-East and Ahoada-West Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The study was guided by three research questions and three corresponding hypotheses. Descriptive survey design was adopted in the study. A total of 350 teachers which constitutes the entire population, participated in the study. Hence, the study was a census. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Teachers Perception of School Counsellors Roles Questionnaire (TPOSCRQ)", designed by the researcher and validated by experts in Guidance Counselling and Educational Measurement and Evaluation from the Rivers State University. Cronbach alpha method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument which yielded reliability indexes of 0.87, 0.74, and 0.85, for the five clusters. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance. Results showed among others that teachers perceived secondary school counsellors' information services as crucial in secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West. Also, the test of hypotheses revealed that the responses of male and female teachers do not differ significantly in their perception of services rendered by guidance counsellors in secondary schools. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that students should be encouraged to study counselling through a robust and intensive scholarship scheme, professional counsellors should be posted to the secondary schools for the exclusive work of counselling services and parents and students should avail themselves of the services of available counsellors in schools and local government centres.

Keywords: Guidance Services, Counsellors, Perception

INTRODUCTION

Counselling and guidance services are services that is aimed at providing personal social, educational and vocational development and self-actualization of individuals who have normal mental health (American School Counsellor Association - ASCA, 2022; Kepceoglu, 2021). The school counsellor, who serves at educational institutions, offers counselling and guidance services aid for the student to know and accept his personality which is constantly developing; to make decisions and choices concerning the upper stage; to deal with the problems he encounters; to make the best use of his potential and thus reach self-actualization (Yesilyaprak, 2020). Guidance and Counselling, or Guidance counselling services refers to the services and programmes that promote personal social, educational and career development. In a school setting, guidance counsellor's role was to attend to the needs of students, parents, guardians, professional associates and the community. Counselling is a process of helping people by assisting them in making decisions and changing behaviour.

Amede and Ihuoma (2018) stated that counselling is concerned with the feelings, attitudes and emotional dispositions of an individual about himself and situations facing him. The author stresses that counselling practice

is mainly concerned with the ways of assisting the individuals to understand himself and the world around him to be able to utilize his/her potentials to the fullest and live a normal and well-adjusted life. According to Owino, (2015), the students' individualistic ideals, interests and emotions need recognition and encouragement. Normally, they are faced with the desire for education and career development. What hinders them from achieving these desires is the influence of a money economy, a pluralistic society, growing materialism and the adoption of western technology. As a result of these influences, they are constantly searching for identity, stability and direction in a changing and uncertain world. Their main concern is to find a coherent and consistent identity so as to function well in the world. There is therefore need to provide them with Guidance and Counselling services to help them make the right choices at every transitional stage. Guidance and Counselling assists students to resolve and cope with conflicts arising from or are bound to arise in a changing society. Students need to be helped to understand themselves in respect to their abilities and interests and with these, the selection of future careers or occupations and/or generally the making of appropriate decisions (Owino, 2015).

Counselling service is one of the services of guidance counsellors in which an individual who is helpless (client) is assisted by counsellor to overcome his/her helplessness through information, interaction, decisions making and conducive environment. The counsellor uses his/her expertise to help the client to overcome his/her problems in order to function effectively in the society. The client is helped to overcome his/her problem by focusing on his/her potentialities that can enable him/her to be adaptive and adjusted. Counsellor exhibits certain qualities while helping the client. He/she creates friendly and warmly atmosphere while receiving the client (rapport). He/she also assures the client of the secrecy of any information revealed by him/her in the process of counselling. Counselling is therefore aimed at assisting the client to overcome his/her problems and become happy and effective (Kenneth, 2013).

Another service of a guidance counsellor is the placement service. Placement service is designed to help an individual to adjust to the next stage in life. This service helps an individual to progress from one stage to another stage in life. For example, an individual who has completed secondary education can be helped to get a job (vocational placement) or secure admission (educational placement) in the university. Placement can be vocational or educational. The counsellor while carrying out placement service takes into cognizance the peculiar needs of the client in relation to his/her needs.

The counsellors are also saddled with the responsibility of referral. This service is designed to help the students get professional attention while solving his/her problem. According to Yusuf, (2021). "referral is the act of transferring an Individual to another person or agency for specialized assistance not available from the original source". In referral service, the counsellor refers the client to where his/her problem can be best solved if the client's problem is above his/her competence. The counsellor does not claim to have solution to all problems as certain problems above his/her competence are referred to where they can be given specialized attention. Types of referral service rendered by counsellors include self-referral which occurs when the client of his/her own volition goes for counselling. The client realizes that he/she has a problem and decides to go for counselling. Also, referral by Others, where parents, teachers, friends or peers persuade a client to visit the counsellor. Here the initiative is that of the people and not the clients. Lastly counsellor referral

whereby the counsellor can invite a client for counselling based on observation or the client's school record. The counsellor can after going through a client's record invite him/her for counselling. However, such invitation should be voluntary. The counsellor should not force the client to visit him/her for counselling

Statement of the Problem

Guidance services in secondary schools are designed primarily to assist students in making wise decisions. These decisions include educational plan, career choice of interest and personal-social development of the study towards ensuring that holistic educational objectives are achieved. Students at the secondary school level tend to exhibit certain psychosocial behaviours ranging from lateness to school, disobedience, stealing, fighting, truancy, rioting, extensive damage to lives and property, sexual immorality, drug abuse and career related problems. These behaviours could disrupt the achievement of educational goals, thereby frustrating teachers' efforts in secondary schools. It is hence imperative that addressing these problems set the conducive pace for counsellors' role in helping students become morally conditioned for learning. However, many teachers believe that counsellors are not necessarily needed in the affairs of the study as far as school administration and teaching is concerned.

The researcher has observed that counsellors seem to be given less consideration in many secondary schools, it explains the reason for high possibility of maladjustment behaviour, among secondary school students. This can further reduce the impact of a classroom teacher on students who needed counselling and not subject content only. Teachers' low perception of school counsellors as crucial part school systems leads to teachers' struggle in students' behavioural adjustments in the classroom instead of a sole focus on their primary objective of teaching. Does it mean that the low students' academic performance is due to low perception of teachers on the role of counsellors in assisting to achieve educational objectives? Consequently, this study determines the teachers' perception of guidance services offered by counsellors in secondary schools in Ahoada-East and Ahoada-West Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine teachers' perception of guidance services offered by counsellors in secondary schools in Ahoada-East and Ahoada-West

Local Government Areas of Rivers State. Specifically, the study attempted to achieve the following objectives:

1. determine teacher’s perceptions of information services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas.
2. examine teacher’s perceptions of counselling services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas.
3. determine teacher’s perceptions of placement services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are teachers’ perceptions of information services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas?
2. What are teacher’s perceptions of counselling services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas?
3. What are teacher’s perceptions of placement services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female teachers on information services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female teachers on counselling services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas

H03: There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female teachers on placement services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. According to Maduabun, (2007), descriptive survey research is suitable for studies dealing with people’s opinion or trends of happenings, and using few people or items in representation of a total group. The study was carried out in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Areas (AELGA and AWELGA) of Rivers State. The population of this study comprises 350 male and female teachers in all the senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Areas of Rivers State, Available statistics from the Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools Board shows that there are 350 teachers in the 34 school as shown on the table below.

Table 1: Population Distribution of Teachers in AELGA and AWLGA

LGA	Number of schools	Number of Teachers		Total
		Males	Females	
AELGA	18	131	71	202
AWLGA	16	85	63	148
TOTAL	34	216	134	350

Source: RSSSSB, 2021

The sample size of this study is all the 350 teachers of the senior secondary schools in Ahoada-East and Ahoada-West Local Government Areas. In other words, the entire population was used for the study since it is not too large and is manageable. Thus, the study was a census. The instrument used in this study was researcher’s structured questionnaire. This instrument was designed after extensive study of related literature. The instrument (questionnaire) is titled: “Teachers Perception of School Counsellors Roles Questionnaire (TPOSCRQ)”. The questionnaire was divided into 2 parts. The response was structured into a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed

(D), and Strongly Disagreed (SD) with numerical values of 4,3,2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from Guidance and counselling and one in measurement and evaluation in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. To establish the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach’s Alpha formula was used. A reliability index of 0.87, 0.76, 0.83, were obtained for the three clusters of the instrument. A total of 350 copies of the questionnaire were administered on the teachers in the 34 secondary schools in study areas, in which all were successfully retrieved. The data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and weighted mean scores and standard deviations to answer

the research questions. Null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistical tool at the 0.05 level of significance. Decision was based on the ratings of criterion mean of 2.50, that is mean items less than 2.50 were termed “disagree” while mean items greater than or equal to 2.50 were termed “Agree”. A null Hypothesis was accepted or retained when the calculated or observed

t-value was lower than the critical t-value (1.96), and rejected if it was higher.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What are teachers’ perceptions of information services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on their Perception of Information Services Offered by Counsellors in Senior Secondary Schools in the Study Areas

S/N	Perception of Teachers on Information Services of Counsellors in Senior Sec. Schools	Male (n= 216)			Female (n= 134)		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmk	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
1.	Counsellor provides information on selection of right subject combinations	2.75	0.99	A	2.64	1.02	A
2.	Counsellor assists students in developing effective study habits	2.63	1.05	A	2.58	1.03	A
3.	Counsellors educates students in overcoming examination anxiety	2.33	1.09	A	2.24	1.08	A
4.	Counsellors provides information on passing exams with high grades	2.72	1.04	A	2.55	1.05	A
5.	New students are not assisted in any way in the choice of subjects.	2.48	1.04	A	2.43	1.08	A
Grand Mean (\bar{X})		2.54	1.05		2.58	1.04	A

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Table 1 shows an item-by-item analysis of mean scores and standard deviation of the responses on the perception of teachers on the information services rendered by Counsellors in senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government area. From the result it could be observed that the respective mean scores of male and female responses on items 1 (2.75, 2.64), item 2 (2.63, 2.58), item 3 (2.33, 2.24) and item 5 (2.48, 2.43) lie within 2.0-2.90, suggesting they agreed. On the whole, the grand mean responses for male and female were 2.48 and 2.42, while the aggregate was 2.45, all of which fall within 2.0-2.90, and therefore indicated

agreement consensus. In other words, male and female teachers perceived that Counsellor provides students with information services on selection of right subject combinations, assists students in developing effective study habits, educates students in overcoming examination anxiety, provides students with information on passing exams with high grades, and new students are not assisted in any way in the choice of subjects.

Research Question 2: What is the perception of teachers on counselling services offered by Counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on their Perception of Counselling Services Offered by Counsellors in Senior Secondary Schools in Ahoada-East and Ahoada-West Local Government Areas.

S/N	Teachers' Perception of Counselling Services Rendered by Counsellors in Senior Secondary Schools	Male (n= 216)		Rmk	Female (n= 134)		Rmks
		\bar{X}	SD		\bar{X}	SD	
1.	Students are provided with information on choosing occupation that matches one's talent.	2.72	1.04	A	2.55	1.05	A
2.	Counsellors do not assist students in making realistic and appropriate vocational choices	2.48	1.04	A	2.43	1.08	A
3.	Students receive information on choosing career of one's interest	2.28	1.00	A	2.26	1.10	A
4.	Counsellors assists students in developing effective job seeking skills	2.36	0.99	A	2.32	1.09	A
5.	Provision of information are not provided on conditions of service about every occupation	2.25	1.04	A	2.34	1.11	A
	Grand Mean (\bar{X})	2.42	1.02	A	2.38	1.09	A

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Table 2 shows the mean scores of the item by item analyses of responses of teachers on perception of the counselling services rendered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in Ahoada-East and Ahoada-West Local Government Areas. Respondents agreed that counsellors provide students with information on choosing occupation that matches their talent. Students receive information on choosing career of their interest and Counsellors assists students in developing effective

job seeking skills. In general, the aggregate grand mean score of 2.40 suggests that teachers perceive that Counsellors render adequate counselling services to students in senior secondary schools Ahoada East and West local Government Areas.

Research Question 3: What is the perception of teachers on placement services rendered by Counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on their Perception of Placement Services Rendered by Counsellors in Senior Secondary Schools in Study Areas.

S/N	Teachers' Perception of Placement Services Rendered by Counsellors in Senior Sec Schools	Male (n= 216)		Rmks	Female (n= 134)		Rmks
		\bar{X}	SD		\bar{X}	SD	
1.	Counsellors assists students to have inter-personal relationship	2.75	0.99	A	2.64	1.02	A
2.	Counsellors do not encourage students against sexual difficulties	2.63	1.05	A	2.58	1.03	A
3.	Counsellors assist students to overcome inability to approach the opposite sex.	2.33	1.09	A	2.24	1.08	A
4.	Counsellors provides information on drug abuse	2.72	1.04	A	2.55	1.05	A
5.	Students are helped in overcoming low self-concept	2.48	1.04	A	2.43	1.08	A
6.	Counsellors assists students to have inter-personal relationship	2.58	1.04	A	2.49	1.04	A
	Grand Mean	2.58	1.04		2.49	1.05	A

Source: Field Data, 2024.

In table 3, the mean scores of items 1 to 6 as well as their aggregate mean scores respectively indicate that respondents are in agreement that counsellors assists students to have inter-personal relationship, counsellors do not encourage students against sexual difficulties, counsellors assist students to overcome inability to approach the opposite sex, counsellors provides information on drug abuse, Students are helped in overcoming low self-concept and counsellors assists students to have inter-personal relationship. The grand

mean response for male is 2.58 and that of females is 2.49, while the aggregate is 2.37, all lying within the range of 3.00 to 2.01, suggesting all respondents agree on the placement services rendered by counsellors in the study areas.

Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the information services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of Ratings of Male and Female Teachers on the Information Services Offered by Counsellors in Senior Secondary Schools in the Study Areas

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal	df	α	t-crit	Decision
Male Teachers	216	2.54	1.05	0.36	348	0.05	1.96	Accept Ho
Female Teachers	134	2.58	1.04					

Source: Data Output, 2024

Table 4 reveals a computed or an observed t-value of 0.36 with a critical equipment of 1.96 with 348 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. Since the observed value is less than the table value, it implies that the computed value is not significant, hence the null hypothesis of no significance difference is retained. In other words, male and female teachers do agree on the

information services offered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Area.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the counselling services rendered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas.

Table 5: t-test of Difference in the Response of Male and Female Teachers on the Counselling Services Rendered by Counsellors in Senior Secondary Schools in the Study Areas

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal	df	α	t-crit	Decision
Male Teachers	215	2.42	1.02	0.34	348	0.05	1.96	Accept Ho
Female Teachers	134	2.38	1.09					

Source: Data Output, 2024

From Table 5, it could be observed that with 348 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance, the critical t-value was 1.96 while the calculated value was 0.34. it could be noted that the computed value is very low compared to the critical value and this suggests that it is

not significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis is upheld meaning, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the counselling services rendered by guidance counsellors in senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada

West Local Government Areas. In other words, male and female teachers do agree on the counselling service rendered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female teachers on the placement services rendered by counsellors in senior secondary schools in the study areas

Table 6: t-test of Analysis on the Rating of Male and Female Teachers in the Placement Services Offered by Counsellors in Senior Secondary Schools in the Study Areas

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal	df	α	t-crit	Decision
Male Teachers	216	2.58	1.04	0.78	348	0.05	1.96	Accept Ho
Female Teachers	134	2.49	1.05					

Source: Data Output, 2024

Table 6 shows that the calculated t-value was 0.78 using the established statistics. At the 0.05 level of significance at 348 degrees of freedom, the artificial value was found to be 1.96, which is far greater than the calculated value. Since the calculated value is less than the critical value, it means that the calculated t-value is not significant and hence the null hypothesis is retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female teachers of Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Areas, on the placement services rendered by guidance counsellors in senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Area.

Discussion of Findings

From research question one, the finding revealed that teacher’s perception is that counsellors in senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Areas render information services to students for proper academic guidance. The information services include among others, selection of right subject combination, developing effective study habits and educate students on how to overcome anxiety. Similar findings were obtained by Eremie and Anugbara (2019) that male and female teachers in Rivers State public secondary schools perceived that counsellors render information services to students to enhance their academic performance in school. This finding is also in line with the findings of Ezenwa (2019) who examined teachers’ perception of the roles of guidance counsellors in secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. With a descriptive design and a sample of over 1,200 teachers randomly selected, the data analyzed revealed that teachers’ perception affect orientation,

awareness and information services of the counsellors in public secondary schools in Edo State. The two studies are related as they examined similar variables with similar types of respondents (teachers). They only differ on area of study. While the present study is in Rivers State, the former was carried out in Edo State.

The findings of the study in research question 2 showed that teachers perceived guidance counsellors as those that offer placement services in senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Areas. This result conforms the assertion of Okeke (2019) who posited that placement services are those that have to do with the process of helping the students to enter and make adjustment in the next stage of development. Counsellors assists students as part of placement service to choose the right subject combination in line with their trait as revealed in the study. This is also the advocacy of Alabi in Awinsong, Dawson, and Gidiglo. (2015) that placement programmes assist graduating students to choose the right course at the university. It is also the view of Eriksson, et al., (2022) the placement services are designed to aid an individual to select and utilize opportunities within the school and in the labour market. The findings of the current study therefore is an embodiment of views and positions of scholars and researchers who have at one time or the other made propositions on the roles of counsellors in the secondary schools.

Moreover, findings from research question 3 showed that male and female teachers perceive counsellors as those

who render counselling services to senior secondary schools in Ahoada East and Ahoada West Local Government Area. This is in agreement with the findings by Brunk (2008) that there is a significant positive perception among teachers regarding the role of the school counsellor, the principal and counsellor – relationship, and the counsellor participation on school leadership team. The current findings are equally in support of Okeke (2019) prescription of the counsellors counselling service as a personalized interaction between the client experiencing a problem and the counsellor who tries to help. In other words, the counselling services provides the forum for interaction between clients and counsellors. In the result of this study, emphasis is on making the individual to have better understanding of himself and his world. The finding further corroborates the position of Demga in Hotaman (2018) that counselling services are regarded as the heartbeat of guidance and counselling since it provides a forum for interaction, a link between the client and the counsellor and counselling services are very critical for the student because they need it to solve their career problem.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that guidance counsellors in secondary schools in Ahoada - East and Ahoada - West local government areas render counselling services but not sufficient. There is also inadequate number of professional counsellors in the area, hence teachers of difference areas of specialization are supplemented for counsellors. Finally, it was concluded that if enough professional counsellors are engaged, the challenges of ill-Behaviours found in the schools could be minimized

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made

1. Government should a robust and intensive scholarship scheme to encourage prospective student to study guidance and counselling. This will increase the rate of guidance counsellors available for secondary school services.
2. School administrators should ensure there is availability of professional counsellors in secondary schools. This will aid the process of achieving holistic learning objectives in the school.

3. School administrators should encourage teachers to allow guidance counsellors to perform their professional duties in schools. This could be achieved by training teachers in the mutualism of achieving learning objectives in the school.

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